

Computation of crystalline state properties of chalcogenide crystals with antiferroite structure

Biswajit Ghatak and Jagdhar Mandal*

University Department of Physics, T. M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007, Bihar, India

E-mail : biswajit.ghatak@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 31 December 2008, accepted 30 December 2010

Abstract : The crystalline state properties such as of cohesive energy, atomization energy, force constant, IR absorption frequency, Debye temperature, Grüneisen parameter, Anderson-Grüneisen parameter and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter for 14 chalcogenide crystals of antiferroite are reported here. These parameters have been obtained by using the Born-Mayer and Varshni-Shukla interionic short-range repulsive interactions. Calculations are also performed for the computation of first order volume dependence of Grüneisen parameter commonly known as second Grüneisen parameter using expressions of higher order derivatives of interaction potential within the frame work of Dugdale and Macdonald theory. The high pressure behaviour of these crystals have also been studied. The results obtained here may add a little to the physics and chemistry of these crystals.

Keywords : Crystalline state properties, Grüneisen parameter, second Grüneisen parameter.

Introduction

The nature of bonding in ionic crystals has been the centre of attraction for theoretical as well as experimental physicists and chemists as it plays a vital role in solid state physics. Several attempts have been made to understand the nature of interaction between the atoms of an ionic crystal and hence to decide the form of interaction potential for such a crystal. Once the reliable form of interaction potential is known, it is possible to study the crystalline state properties of chalcogenide crystal. The crystal state properties of chalcogenides have been studied by several workers. But these investigators employed the interaction models¹⁻⁴ with repulsive parts that are either inverse power functions or exponential functions or phenomenological in nature. But none of these are capable enough of explaining all the observed macroscopic properties of diatomic crystals. The search for the interaction potential function satisfying the essential requirements of ideal potential function⁵ continues. The chalcogenides of Li, Na, K and Rb are suitable host crystals for transition metal ions and rare earth ions⁶. A knowledge of interionic potentials in host crystals is of considerable value. The alkali chalcogenides which crystallize

in antiferroite structure are relatively unexplored.

In the present paper we have used the Born-Mayer⁷ and Varshni-Shukla⁸ short-range repulsive potential to evaluate the crystalline state properties of chalcogenide crystals. The reason for selecting these models lies in their suitability⁹ of evaluating their state properties as well as molecular state properties. Moreover, these potentials fulfill the fundamental physical requirements of an ideal potential.

Method of analysis :

Crystal energy : The crystal lattice energy per ion pair can be expressed as

$$\Phi(r) = \Phi_c + \Phi_v + \Phi_{SR} \quad (1)$$

Here Φ_c is the long-range electrostatic coulomb energy with Madelung constant A . It is given by

$$\Phi_c = -Az_1z_2e^2/r \quad (2)$$

where z_1e and z_2e are the electrostatic charges on the ion pairs and r is the interionic separation.

The second term, Φ_v , on the R.H.S. of the eq. (1) represents the van der Waals energy expressed as

$$\Phi_v = -C/r^6 - D/r^8 \quad (3)$$

where C and D are van der Waals (vdw) dipole-dipole and dipole quadrupole co-efficients and are given by

$$C = S_{+-} c_{+-} + S_{++} c_{++} + S_{--} c_{--}$$

and

$$D = T_{+-} d_{+-} + T_{++} d_{++} + T_{--} d_{--} \quad (4)$$

Lattice sums S_{ij} and T_{ij} have been taken from Tosi¹⁰ and vdw co-efficients c_{ij} and d_{ij} are taken from Shankar, Singh and Agarwal¹¹.

The last term Φ_{SR} on the R.H.S. eq. (1), is expressed as

$$\Phi_{SR} = S/r^m \exp(-\lambda r^n) \quad (5)$$

where S and λ are potential parameters evaluated by applying the following crystal stability conditions :

$$\Phi'(r_0) = 0$$

and

$$\Phi''(r_0) = 9kr_0/\beta \quad (6)$$

where k = crystals structure constant and β = isothermal compressibility.

In the above equations r_0 is the equilibrium interionic separation in the lattice and the primes denote derivatives with respect to r .

The application of the above conditions to the potentials function yields the expression for the potential parameters :

$$S = \frac{r^m [Az_1z_2e^2/r_0 + 6C/r_0^6 + 8D/r_0^8]}{\exp(-\lambda r^n) (m + n\lambda r^n)} \quad (7)$$

and

$$A = \frac{X + n - 2m - 1 + [(X + n - 2m - 1)^2 - \{4m(M + 1)\} - X]^{1/2}}{r^n 2n} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\lambda = \frac{9kr_0^3 + 2Az_1z_2e^2/r_0 + 42C/r_0^6 + 72D/r_0^8}{Az_1z_2e^2/r_0 + 6C/r_0^6 + 8D/r_0^8} \quad (9)$$

where

$$z_1 = 2 \text{ and } z_2 = 1 \text{ for alkali chalcogenide crystals}$$

$$\text{and } m = 0, n = 1 \text{ for BM potential}$$

$$m = 2, n = 1 \text{ for VS mode!}$$

The last term Φ_{SR} eq. (1) is the short-range overlap repulsive energy dominant in diatomic crystals. The short-range repulsive potential perturbs the spherically symmetric closed shell of an ion in a lattice as the ions are brought closer so that outer electron shells began to overlap. An additional characteristic repulsive force becomes operative resulting from the overlapping of the ions. This repulsive force opposes the Coulombian attractive force operating between the positive and the negative ions and causes them to come to equilibrium at finite value of the interionic distance (r_0). This repulsive force in an ion becomes dominant at a very short distance, so it is known as short-range repulsive potential (SRRP). The exact form of SRRP in literature is still lacking.

Cohesive energy :

The cohesive energy W per mole is related to the interaction potential energy function $\Phi(r)$ by

$$W = -N \Phi(r) \quad (10)$$

where N is Avogadro's number.

Force constant (f), IR absorption frequency (ν_0) and Debye temperature (θ_D) :

The force constant f is defined¹² as

$$f = 1/3 [\Psi''(r_0) + 2r_0^{-1} \Psi'(r_0)] \quad (11)$$

where $\Psi(r)$ is the non-Coulombic part of $\Phi(r)$ and r_0 is the equilibrium interionic distance in crystalline states.

The IR absorption frequency (ν_0) is given¹² by

$$\nu_0 = 1/2\pi(fm)^{1/2}$$

where m is the reduced mass.

Once the value of ν_0 is obtained, the Debye temperature θ_D can be calculated from the relation,

$$\theta_D = h \nu_0/k$$

where h is the Planck's constant and k is the Boltzmann constant.

Grüneisen parameter, Anderson-Grüneisen parameter and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter :

The Grüneisen parameter γ is the first significant measure of the anharmonicity in solids. It is related to $\Phi(r)$ by¹²

$$\gamma_{DM} = (-1/6)[r_0 \Phi'''(r_0) / \Phi''(r_0)] \quad (12)$$

according to Slater theory²¹

$$\gamma_s = (-2/3) - (-1/6)[r_0 \Phi'''(r_0)/\Phi''(r_0)] \quad (13)$$

where $\Phi''(r)$ and $\Phi'''(r)$ refer to the second and third derivatives of $\Phi(r)$.

Anderson-Grüneisen parameters δ have been computed using Chang's expression¹² connecting γ and δ which was derived on the basis of Dugdale and Macdonald formula¹⁴ relating γ to the change of compressibility with volume. Sharma²² has derived similar expression for δ for a solid which is written as

$$\delta = 2\gamma + \frac{1}{3}$$

The values of the Moelwyn-Hughes parameter C_1 have been computed for the potential $\Phi(r)$ using the relation¹²

$$C_1 = 1 - (r_0^3 \beta / 27V) \Phi'''(r_0) \quad (14)$$

where β is the compressibility of the crystals.

Second Grüneisen parameter :

The first order volume dependence of the Grüneisen parameter commonly known as the second Grüneisen parameter is fundamental to the study of many basic phenomena in solids. It is an additional measure of the anharmonicity in solids. γ and q can be used to make predictions of a variety of physical properties such as the equation of state of a material and are related to thermodynamic properties. These are also important in the study of thermo-elastic properties in terms of shock-waves. The latter property is especially relevant to the study of the geophysics of the earth.

In general, the Grüneisen parameter is a function of both temperature and volume. The temperature of Grüneisen parameter for a large number of diatomic crystals can be fairly determined either experimentally or theoretically.

In this communication an attempt has been made to calculate q for chalcogenide crystals using Born-Mayer and Varshini-Shukla forms of interaction models within the framework of Dugdale and Macdonald theory (DM).

Grüneisen parameter (γ) based on DM theory valid at all pressures may be expressed as

$$\gamma = -1 - V/2 (\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P/9V^2) (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)^{-1} \quad (14)$$

The second Grüneisen parameter (q) derived from eq. (1) is written as¹⁵

$$q = -V/2\gamma[(\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P/9V^2) (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)^{-1} + (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V) (\partial^3 P / \partial V^3 - 10/V^2 \partial P / \partial V + 20P/V^3) - V(\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P/9V^2) (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)^{-2} (\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 + 2/3V \partial P / \partial V - 2/3 P/V^2)] \quad (15)$$

Hildebrand equation of state¹⁶ can be used to express γ and q in terms of derivatives of potential energy function.

For crystals with antiferroite structure

$$P = -\partial\Phi/\partial V = (-1/3kr^2)\Phi'(r) \quad (16)$$

$$\partial P / \partial V = (-1/9k^2r^4)(\Phi'' - 2/r \Phi'(r)) \quad (17)$$

$$\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 = (-1/27k^3r^6) [\Phi''' - 6/r \Phi'' + 10/r^2 \Phi'] \quad (18)$$

$$\partial^3 P / \partial V^3 = (-1/81k^4r^8) [\Phi'''' - 12/r \Phi'''' + 52/r^2 \Phi'' - 80/r^3 \Phi'] \quad (19)$$

where the primes denote the derivatives of $\Phi(r)$ with respect to interionic separation.

Equation of state of chalcogenides :

The high pressure behaviour of these crystals is investigated by determining the compression values of these crystals by using Murnaghan logarithmic equation of state expressed as

$$V/V_0 = \exp[(-1/B'_0) \log_e \{(PB'_0/B_0) + 1\}] \quad (20)$$

where B_0 and B'_0 are isothermal bulk modulus and its pressure derivatives, both referred to zero pressure²⁰. The high pressure behaviour of these crystals have been shown below in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. A compression curves V/V_0 pressure P (Kbar) for chalcogenide crystals based on present interionic potential models.

Results and discussion

The latest information on alkali chalcogenide crystals is far from complete but this work tries to add a little to the knowledge of these crystals by predicting several crystalline state properties such as cohesive energy (W), force constant, IR absorption frequency (ν_0), Debye temperature, Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ), Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) and second Grüneisen parameter (q) respectively.

Born-Mayer and Varshni-Shukla forms of short-range repulsive potential have been used to compute W of chalcogenide crystals and their values are listed in Table 1. It is found that the cohesive energy of a $AO > AS > ASe > Ate$ for both the models. Only a few attempts have been made^{17,18} to determine their cohesive energy using Born-Mayer model.

Table 1. Calculated properties of chalcogenide crystals Cohesive energy (kJ mol^{-1}) and calculated values

Crystal	BM	VS	Calcd. values ²⁰	Calcd. values ¹⁷
Li ₂ O	2882.49	2835.83	2879.94	-
Na ₂ O	2531.33	2514.57	2480.52	2535.12
K ₂ O	2326.83	2321.72	2283.96	2244.9
Rb ₂ O	2309.18	2307.02	2265.06	2160.48
Li ₂ S	2384.86	2357.86	2393.16	2483.46
Na ₂ S	2117.43	2095.70	2118.48	2209.2
K ₂ S	1946.88	1935.71	1926.96	1992.06
Rb ₂ S	1916.59	1908.30	1892.94	1942.92
Li ₂ Se	2242.97	2210.33	2250.78	-
Na ₂ Se	1995.83	1969.76	1998.78	-
K ₂ Se	1835.31	1820.40	1821.96	-
Li ₂ Te	2116.90	2095.20	2124.36	-
Na ₂ Te	1891.69	1873.12	1898.40	-
K ₂ Te	1733.96	1720.82	1734.60	-

The present values of W compare well with the calculated values of Jain-Shanker¹⁹ and Morris¹⁷. It is observed that the inclusion of van der Waals terms improves the results expectedly and given the better agreement. Out of the two Born-Mayer and Varshni-Shukla models, the latter presents a better result. Atomization energy are not reported for these crystals mainly because of the uncertainties in the values of electron affinities for chalcogenide ions.

genide ions.

Table 2 lists the calculated values of f , ν_0 and θ_D . And no comparison can be had for the agreement between the theoretical and experimental values as the experimental values are not available in the literature. The present calculation shows that van der Waals energy is important for heavier crystals. It is observed that the two models give almost identical results of f , ν_0 and θ_D .

Table 2. Calculated properties of chalcogenide crystals (a) Force constant f (Nm^{-1}), (b) IR absorption frequency ν_0 (10^{12} Hz) and (c) Debye temperature θ_D (K)

Crystal	F.C.	I.R.F.	Decom. temp.
Li ₂ O	17.35	23.21	1114.61
Na ₂ O	15.45	15.75	756.35
K ₂ O	17.66	15.36	737.38
Rb ₂ O	23.34	16.21	778.09
Li ₂ S	10.95	16.99	815.86
Na ₂ S	7.95	9.48	455.18
K ₂ S	7.66	8.11	389.58
Rb ₂ S	8.19	7.29	350.22
Li ₂ Se	8.43	14.09	676.68
Na ₂ Se	6.16	7.24	347.50
K ₂ Se	5.72	5.76	276.42
Li ₂ Te	7.95	13.47	646.65
Na ₂ Te	5.77	6.70	321.54
K ₂ Te	4.94	5.00	240.04

The calculated values of γ , δ , C_1 and q have been listed in Table 3. There is no experimental data to draw comparison. But the present results indicate that γ depends upon the specific volume since the values tend to increase as we move from oxides to tellurides.

We have investigated the high-pressure behaviour of these crystals. The equation works well up to very high pressure. The compression curves are given in Fig. 1. The graphical behaviour of force constant and cohesive energy is shown in Fig. 2. The graphical behaviour of reduced mass and IR frequency, force constant and interatomic distance are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. The experimental data for the compressions of chalcogenide crystals are not available in the literature and hence it is not possible to draw experimental curves for these

Table 3. Calculated properties of chalcogenide crystals

Values of Grüneisen parameter (γ : dimensionless), second Grüneisen parameter (q : dimensionless), Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ : dimensionless) and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1 : dimensionless)

Crystal	γ_{DM}		γ_s		q		δ_c		δ_s		C_1	
	BM	VS	BM	VS	BM	VS	BM	VS	BM	AH	BM	VS
Li ₂ O	1.13	1.26	1.47	1.60	0.34	0.14	2.27	2.53	0.67	0.47	3.27	3.53
Na ₂ O	1.50	1.59	1.84	1.92	0.47	0.33	3.01	3.18	0.81	0.67	4.01	4.18
K ₂ O	2.17	2.22	2.50	2.55	0.72	0.63	4.34	4.44	1.06	0.97	5.34	5.44
Rb ₂ O	2.84	2.87	3.17	3.21	0.92	0.89	5.68	5.75	1.29	1.22	6.68	6.75
Li ₂ S	1.27	1.38	1.60	1.71	0.41	0.23	2.53	2.76	0.75	0.56	3.53	3.76
Na ₂ S	1.31	1.42	1.64	1.75	0.46	0.27	2.62	2.83	0.79	0.60	3.62	3.83
K ₂ S	1.63	1.71	1.96	2.04	0.56	0.42	3.25	3.42	0.90	0.75	4.25	4.42
Rb ₂ S	1.81	1.89	2.15	2.22	0.63	0.51	3.63	3.77	0.96	0.84	4.63	4.77
Li ₂ Se	1.15	1.29	1.49	1.62	0.44	0.21	2.31	2.57	0.77	0.54	3.31	3.57
Na ₂ Se	1.20	1.32	1.53	1.65	0.48	0.24	2.39	2.64	0.81	0.58	3.39	3.64
K ₂ Se	1.45	1.55	1.78	1.88	0.52	0.34	2.90	3.09	0.85	0.68	3.90	4.09
Li ₂ Te	1.31	1.42	1.65	1.75	0.45	0.26	2.62	2.84	0.78	0.60	3.62	3.84
Na ₂ Te	1.33	1.44	1.67	1.77	0.47	0.28	2.67	2.88	0.80	0.62	3.67	3.88
K ₂ Te	1.48	1.58	1.81	1.91	0.54	0.36	2.96	3.15	0.87	0.70	3.96	4.15

Fig. 2. A plot of force constant versus cohesive energy for alkali chalcogenide crystals.

Fig. 4. A plot of interionic distance versus force constant for alkali chalcogenide crystals.

Fig. 3. A plot of reduced mass versus IR frequency for alkali chalcogenide crystals.

crystals. The theoretical results reported here may be useful for experimentalists in crystals of alkali chalcogenides. From our study of crystal structure properties of diatomic crystals we can develop four models in parallel to Einstein and Debye force model.

Conclusion :

Born-Mayer and Varshni-Shukla forms of interaction potential have been applied to get different crystalline state properties of chalcogenide crystals. The latter model gives encouraging result and may prove useful for fur-

ther computation of the properties of such crystals. The theoretical results of some crystals (no experimental values available in literature) may useful for experimentalists.

Acknowledgement

We are extremely thankful to Professor Md. M. M. Hasan for his keen interest in the completion of this work.

References

1. K. P. Thakur, *Austrian. J. Phys.*, 1977, **30**, 323.
2. R. Rydberg, *Z. Phys.*, 1931, **73**, 376.
3. J. Shankar and M. Kumar, *Phys. Status Solidi (b)*, 1987, **142**, 325.
4. R. Narayan and S. Ramaseshan, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1976, **37**, 395.
5. Y. P. Varshini and R. C. Shukla, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1963, **35**, 130.
6. W. Buhner and H. Bill, *J. Phys.*, 1980, **C13**, 5495.
7. M. Born and J. E. Mayer, *Z. Phys.*, 1932, **A75**, 1.
8. Y. P. Varshini and R. P. C. Shukla, *J. Chem. Phys. (USA)*, 1978, **69**, 670.
9. J. Mandal and B. Ghatak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 145.
10. M. P. Tosi, *Solid State Phys.*, 1964, **16**, 1.
11. J. Shankar, G. G. Agrawal and R. P. Singh, *J. Chem. Phys. (USA)*, 1978, **69**, 670.
12. B. Ghatak and J. Mandal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 820.
13. Y. A. Chang, *Phys. Chem. Solidi*, 1967, **28**, 697.
14. J. C. Dugdale and D. K. C. Macdonald, *Phys. Rev.*, 1953, **89**, 832.
15. M. I. Alam, M. S. Ali and M. M. Hasan, *Ind. J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1992, **30**, 310.
16. J. H. Hildebrand, *Z. Phys. (German)*, 1931, **44**, 4618.
17. D. F. C. Morris, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1957, **A242**, 116; *Acta Cryst.*, 1958, **11**, 163; *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1958, **5**, 264.
18. G. G. Agrawal, O. P. Sharma, H. P. Sharma and J. Shanker, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2131.
19. V. K. Jain and J. Shanker, *Phys. Stat. Solidi (b)*, 1982, **114**, 271.
20. O. L. Anderson, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1966, 547.
21. J. C. Slater, "Introduction to Chemical Physics".
22. M. N. Sharma, *Phys. Stat. Solidi (b)*, 1977, **82K**, 53.